

Architecture a Difficult Course to Study: Myth or Reality?

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Abstract:- This study investigates the claim that studying architecture is challenging. The most challenging course to study across the board is architecture. This article examines some universities in south-west Nigeria, examining the perspectives and opinions of the architecture students at six various institutions in the region, to identify the root of the issue and provide alleviating solutions. The research design used in the study was descriptive. The target audience consisted of five equity researchers who conducted thirty interviews with each respondent on six university campuses. In addition to secondary data from books, e-books, websites, and unpublished academic articles, the study also employed primary data from direct interviews. The article asserts the necessity of updating Nigeria's architectural education curriculum to enable students to effectively meet the challenges of their study.

Keywords:- Architecture, Difficult, Course, Study.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Background of the Study

Education is the process of training man to fulfill his aim by fully exercising all the faculties as a member of society. Aristotle

Education is a combination of growth and human development with social legacy. Kohn Tamm and Gunning

Architecture is a way of seeing, thinking and questioning our world and our place in it." - Thom Mayne in his Pritzker Prize Acceptance Speech

Architecture is about serving others through the design of the built environment." - Kevin J Singh in "21 Rules for A Successful Life in Architecture"

In Nigeria, there are three levels of education: primary, secondary, and tertiary. At the tertiary level, students study architecture, among other subjects.

The Nigeria College of Arts, Science, and Technology's founded in the year 1952 was situated in Ibadan, the capital of Nigeria's Western Region, and marked the beginning of architecture education in that country. It moved in 1955 to Zaria in northern Nigeria. In 1961, the initial class of diploma graduates was conferred. The institution was elevated in 1962 to become Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, a full-fledged university. The curriculum was revised, and graduates were given the Bachelor of Architecture degree, which was linked to the RIBA in the same way as the former Diploma degree (Royal Institute of British Architects). Up until 1968, when the course curriculum was once again divided into two tiers with the offer of a master's degree, the affiliation with the Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA) was retained. In 1969, the new program began. The faculty of the institutions was predominately made up of architects from Eastern and Western Europe throughout these times. Nigeria's second architectural education era; also known as the "Semi-colonial Age of Experimentation" by Uji (2001). With a majority of Nigerian faculty members, fourteen schools of architecture have been founded in the nation since 1979.

➤ Statement of Problems:

It is important to note that Several studies have looked at the difficulties that students at various academic levels and levels of study face. Yet, despite the idea that studying architecture is tough, there has not been much or any research to investigate this idea among students studying architecture in Nigeria. So, the purpose of this study is to explore this claim.

➤ Aim of Research

The purpose of this study is to examine these issues and offer a comprehensive solution for Nigerian architecture students.

➤ Research Objectives:

Examine the claim that studying architecture in Nigeria is challenging to see if it is true or not. Look at how architectural education affects students in Nigeria. Identify

the greatest answer to the issue Nigerian architecture students are facing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to a study conducted in Indiana University architectural design course demonstrates that studio sessions are just as demanding as traditional architecture lectures. Hanafi (2016) offers evidence for the claim that this course is a requirement for the design course the following semester. Students are assigned design homework that must be finished in the allotted amount of time. Nonetheless, some students are still stressed by the amount of time allotted for the design studio assignment (Hanafi, 2016). One responder who was questioned, according to Hill (2016)'s paper, said that two of his course mates had committed suicide because of the burden their workloads had put on them. From the findings of the Architect Journal's (AJ) annual student survey, Waite and Braidwood (2016) report that the stresses of architectural education are having a terrible impact on the mental health of the future architects. This assertion is demonstrated when one of the architects questioned: As comparison to other majors, the student claimed they had more work to do on top of attending courses for 20 or more hours each week (Graff, 2016). Stress is the effect of lack of sleep which finally led to the development of a pessimistic outlook on college and university life (Graff, 2016).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ Introduction

This chapter explains the methodology that was used in carrying out the research work. Crucial issues that were discussed in this chapter include research design, target population, sample size, data collection and techniques, interviews, data analysis techniques, and ethical considerations.

➤ Research Design

The research design refers to the plan, and the structure of investigation students to obtain relevant answers to research questions. This study involved a case study using a direct interview with Architectural students in six different universities situated in south-west Nigeria. The institutions are Federal university of Technology Akure, University of Lagos, Bell University of Technology, Covenant University, and Obafemi Awolowo University. The study applied a descriptive research design. Descriptive research design is a systematic, empirical inquiry into which the researcher does not have direct control of independent variables as their manifestation has already occurred or because they are reflecting the state of happenings and qualify the obtained findings using quantitative analysis (Mugenda and Mugenda 2003).

➤ Target Population

The study population comprises of 5 researchers conducting interviews in 6 different universities with focus on 30 students per university. Therefore 30 students in each

of the 6 universities made the target population of 180 respondents.

➤ Data Collection Instruments

The researcher employed two data-collecting methods in the study. These entailed

- *Direct interview*
- *Scholarly Journals*

The main technique applied by the study was the direct interview which was conducted with the respondents.

➤ Data Collection Procedure

The study involved the preparation of a project proposal on which all five researchers in the group agreed. 20 students were interviewed on each of the campuses.

Also, Scholarly journals were reviewed to give us an idea of the topic based on previously researched related topics.

➤ Data Analysis Techniques

All data from the different interviews were gathered to generate descriptive information about the respondents that participated in the study and to illustrate the general trend of findings on the various variables that were under investigation.

➤ Ethical Considerations

During this research process, the researcher upheld integrity and high moral standards. The researcher sought permission from the head of the department of Architecture in each institution before engaging students in interviews. The researcher kept time, respected the respondent's feedback, and decision, and treated the information given by the respondents with confidentiality.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

➤ Introduction

This chapter includes data analysis presentation and interpretation. The chapter is presented in the following manner, characteristic of respondents by their experience in studying architecture in Nigerian institutions.

➤ Background Characteristics from Respondents

The study targeted a sample size Of 180 respondents from six south-west Nigeria universities which is adequate to carry out an investigation and data analysis for this study to ascertain if is a myth or reality that Architecture is a difficult course to study in the region.

➤ Key Data From Respondents.

- *In Nigeria, studying architecture is challenging. True or false?*
Most students think it to be true.

- *Why do you think architecture is a challenging field to study in Nigeria?*

Time was cited by students as a key obstacle to learning architecture. They emphasized the need for manual drawing as opposed to current computer-aided drafting for the job of the design studio.

Students complained that there are too many borrowed classes, such as calculus, that do not apply to them and just add to their already hectic schedules by adding extra work.

Most of the students responded, "It is challenging largely because of extended studying hours, which convert into long working hours owing to loads of take-home tasks.

"Bad studio conditions were cited by most students interviewed on the Federal University of Technology campus as a significant challenge to studying architecture. They argued that working in a cramped studio for extended hours was necessary.

Several students in Nigeria perceived architecture as a challenging course because they thought grades were determined by the opinions of the teachers.

Students claimed that one of the biggest challenges for those studying architecture in Nigeria is the absence of basic facilities like security and reliable energy in their institution. They denounced the students' need to use a mobile phone flashlight to see well when working on their homework at home and the anxiety that overtakes them when they leave the studio after dark owing to the campus's vulnerability.

Most of the part 1 (100 level) students stated that they find architecture difficult because of a lack of previous knowledge of architectural-related subjects in secondary school. The students said that they just found themselves studying architecture against their own will as it is the course given to them to study during the admission process

Architecture is seen as a financially draining course because of the regular need to spend on expensive drawing materials

Most of the part 1 (100 level) students claimed that their lack of prior understanding of architecturally relevant courses in secondary school makes them find architecture challenging. The students said that because studying architecture was required as part of the admissions process, they simply found themselves doing it against their choice.

Because students frequently need to spend money on expensive drawing supplies, architecture is perceived as a financially taxing discipline.

- *What effects does architectural education have on students?*

Social Factor: According to the students, one of the disadvantages of studying architecture is social deprivation. Students in architecture find it challenging to interact with their peers in other areas because the course is time-consuming.

Stress on the mind and body: Architecture students must perform lengthy, overnight shifts, which inevitably puts them under stress on the mind and body.

Finances: According to students, one of the largest expenditures connected with studying architecture is daily expenses. The requirement to purchase drawing supplies on a university campus located in a nation with an unsteady economy makes it difficult for students to study architecture.

- *Why do you think Architecture is not a difficult course to study in Nigeria?*

It depends on your interests, several pupils said. If you have an interest in art and design, it is not at all difficult. Several students claimed that because it is their only assignment on campus and cannot be coupled with anything else, the course is not challenging to study.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents by Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	TRUE	TRUE %	FALSE	FALSE %
Male	111	92	82.88	19	17.12
Female	69	57	82.61	12	17.39
TOTAL	180	149		31	
PERCENTAGE		82.78%		17.22%	

According to the research's breakdown of respondents by gender, 111 male students were questioned, and 82.88% claimed that studying architecture in Nigeria is tough; 17.12% replied that it is not a challenging subject to learn. Also, the table showed that 82.61% of 69 female students affirmed that architecture is a difficult course to study in Nigeria, and 17.39% of 69 female students disagreed and said it is a myth.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by Level of Degree

CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	TRUE	TRUE %	FALSE	FALSE %
Undergraduate	120	114	95	6	5
Postgraduate	60	40	66.67	20	33.33
TOTAL	180	154		26	
PERCENTAGE		85.5%		14.5%	

Research distribution of respondents by the level of degree shows 95% of 120 undergraduate students interviewed said Architecture is a difficult course to study in Nigeria and 5% of 120 undergraduate students stated that Architecture is not a difficult course to study. Also, the table showed that 66.67% of 60 postgraduate students affirmed that Architecture is a difficult course to study in Nigeria, while 33.33% of 60 postgraduate students disagreed and said it is a myth.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

➤ Conclusion

This study supports the idea that students find studying architecture challenging for a variety of reasons. Thus, it is safe to assume that, based on the research findings; the claim that "architecture is a tough course to study in Nigeria" is accurate.

➤ Recommendations

- *Students should acquire time management skills. Among all other social activities, studying architecture should come first.*
- *To lessen the stress on students by lowering the number of unrelated courses, the architectural curriculum needs to be reviewed and rebuilt.*
- *To ensure that students may study easily and safely, schools where architecture is studied need to improve on necessities like a steady supply of energy and security.*
- *To encourage students to work in the studio rather than their dorms, architecture studios should be kept comfortable.*

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